

Task Description

Presentation:

This document contains instructions on performing the study tasks. As it is an observational study, whenever possible, express your doubts, in this way the researcher can evaluate the results obtained. Ask and comment on what you think is necessary.

Contextualization:

The Software Product Lines (LPS) are a development strategy applied to a family of software products, whose characteristics and functionalities are similar, thus increasing the support for reuse, allowing the development of software with less time to market, lower costs, and better quality.

Dynamic Software Product Lines (LPSD) are based on LPS, however, they adopt a set of techniques that allow dynamic adaptation of resources, with variability being managed at runtime.

The Feature Model assists in the management and individual validation of the configuration of LPS products. Furthermore, depending on the level of abstraction, a feature model can allow the visualization of the most prominent features of the product, contributing to software improvements and domain analysis.

Finally, dynamic reconfiguration is the ability of a system to manage runtime variability. Runtime variability defines the product design options visible to customers and system users, who can select from the available configurable options.

Tasks:

The feature model used for this experimentation is the Nexus DSPL. The model can be found on the DyMMer web repository by going to <https://dymmerufc.github.io/#/fmodel-manager/5cb66afc0268200004948a7e>. After opening the indicated feature model, follow the instructions below to perform the experiment:

- a) **Analyzing the feature model:** The initial task consists of analyzing the feature model, its structure and organization, and the set of existing

constraints. After this initial analysis, locate the button called "**OPEN ADAPTATION MECHANISM**" and click to open the method.

- b) **Identify context agents:** The identification of agents is performed with the analysis of the feature model. You should observe which features are related to agents such as sensors, drivers, etc. After identifying a new agent, click on the "Add Agent" button and enter it as indicated. After creating an agent, you can define contexts for it, if there are no apparent contexts, you must create one called "Power" to indicate that the agent is on or off. This process can be performed by clicking on the "Add Context" button inside the agent's card.
- c) **Linking contexts to features:** Once the process of creating agents and contexts is finished, you must link them to the corresponding features. To do this, locate the feature you want to link to a context, click on "Link Agent", and a selection box will open. Then select the agent, context, and context value. Repeat the process until all contexts are linked.
- d) **Adaptation simulation:** To carry out the simulation, click on the "Simulate" button. When starting the simulation, the interface will change and new buttons will be displayed. In the context agents panel, you must turn the contexts on and off and observe if the model features are activated or deactivated.

This form aims to collect information from each participant about the use of the fitting method.

1. Do you agree that the use of the Adaptation Method helped in the modeling of Context Agents? Justify your answer.
 - a. I totally agree
 - b. partially agree
 - c. undecided
 - d. I partially disagree
 - e. I totally disagree
2. Do you agree that the Adaptation Method allowed the visualization of the reconfiguration process after the context change? Justify your answer.
 - a. I totally agree
 - b. partially agree

- c. undecided
 - d. I partially disagree
 - e. I totally disagree
3. In your opinion, what was the effort to identify the agents related to the feature model? Justify your answer.
 - a. High
 - b. Medium
 - c. Short
 4. In your opinion, what was the effort to model the contexts of each identified agent? Justify your answer.
 - a. High
 - b. Medium
 - c. Low
 5. Regarding the adaptation simulation process, do you believe that: Justify your answer.
 - a. Helped understand what settings the model will assume from each context change
 - b. It made it difficult to understand, some simulations were confusing or the information was insufficient.
 6. What was your main difficulty in using the tool?
 7. What are the advantages and disadvantages of the Adaptation Method?
 8. What suggestions would you have to improve the Adaptation Method?